

Selfie Taking Behavior and Self-esteem among Adolescents

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Abstract:- The purpose of the present study is to assess the selfie taking behavior and self-esteem among adolescents. The study assesses the relationship between selfie taking behavior and self-esteem and assess whether there are significant differences in gender with respect to selfie taking behavior and self-esteem. A sample of 80 adolescents (40 males, 40 females) aged between 15-24 years participated in this study. Selfie Behavior scale (SBS) by Janarthanan & Mark D. Griffiths (2017) and The Rosenberg's self-esteem scale (RSES) by Rosenberg, M. (1965) were used to measure the variables in the study. Pearson's correlation coefficient and independent sample t-test were used for statistical analysis of data. The findings indicated that the Selfie taking behaviour was not correlated with self-esteem. There were no significant gender differences in selfie taking behaviour and self-esteem among adolescents.

Keywords:- *Selfie, Behaviour, Self-Esteem, Adolescents.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence, the period between puberty and maturity, is the most critical and exciting time of a person's life. Through the physical, psychological, and cognitive changes taking place in their body, they come to understand who they truly are and where they fit in. The quick changes and advances that take place make this shifting a challenging experience sometimes. Children start to develop the ability for abstract and logical cognition in the early stages of adolescence. They start using these newly learned skills to analyse moral dilemmas and try to distinguish between right and wrong. (Evan G, 2023) This recent development also exhibits a concerned sensitivity to aesthetics and outward appearances. The emotional component of growth which ends up being the most challenging adds to this. Frustration could also be brought on by the expansion of numerous fields. The individual's quest for independence is a major source of contention, frequently trying the patience of teachers, parents, and other guardians with comparable authority and responsibility (Biolcati & Cani, 2015). One element that can both resolve and exacerbate such disagreements is communication. Another facet of adolescent life is the development of the social and psychological systems. These two variables are interrelated; an imbalance in one can result in conflict in the other. Teenagers who discover they don't have any peers or aren't a part of any peer group may experience severe feelings of isolation and uniqueness.

Common social networking sites usage such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter etc has increased rapidly over the past few years (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Its relative novelty is linked to the occurrence of new psychological and collective phenomena, some of which have yet to be carefully explored (Sorokowski et al., 2015). A Selfie is defined as a self-portrait, particularly one taken with a smartphone or webcam and posted on social media. Selfies can be used to compensate the feelings of loneliness, boredom, or relationship problems, much like compulsive buying and smartphone addiction. The various motives behind the selfie taking are the documentation, memories, attention, validation, positive comments from people and self-approval which thereby increase one's self esteem to post and take. A regularly selfie taking person will have an urge to take selfies daily. As a result of having access to other people's ideas, viewpoints, and evaluations on social media platforms like Facebook, Snapchat, and Instagram, young people nowadays have a positive perspective on the idea of selfies. People crave other people's approval as a result of the immediate nature of social media, which only serves to confirm their notion of physical allure. Self-esteem and narcissistic qualities make people more inclined to update selfies because they seek attention and approval from internet users, with thereby increasing the self-esteem (Hughes et al., 2012). Due to the inherent chance to compare oneself to others and the potential for receiving negative or no feedback, social media may contribute to poor self-esteem. According to (Barry et al., 2015) posting selfies was a fairly common occurrence with some participants sharing hundreds of them. lack of correlation between self-reported narcissism and self-esteem and overall selfie postings suggests that other dimensions are more accurate predictors of this particular and very recent self-presentation behaviour.

Self-esteem is defined as an individual's overall self-evaluation of one's own worth (Rosenberg, M., 1965). Low self-esteem can appear in many different ways, and there are two different sorts of it. If someone has poor self-esteem, they could have a pessimistic attitude on life and feel out of control. A person with great self-esteem doesn't waste time thinking about the past or the future and instead makes a significant effort to live in the present. Self-esteem issues, trouble navigating social situations, and an unwillingness to tolerate criticism can all stem from having too high of self-esteem. Selfitis is a mental disorder where a person has an obsessional want to capture images of themselves and post them on social media as a way to compensate for low self-esteem and to close intimacy distances. Some researchers

have found that the individuals low in self-esteem engaged in more self-promoting behaviours on Facebook (including self-promoting photos) as compared with individuals with higher self-esteem (Sorokowski et al., 2015). It is simple for people to just partly represent themselves in selfies when they try to post them on social media (Bareket-Bojmel et al., 2016). When you begin comparing yourself excessively to other people, which social media seems to be made for, self-esteem frequently suffers. As a result, individuals frequently choose the features they want to draw attention to in their pictures, which will boost their self-esteem. Controversial, other studies have pointed out that low and high self-esteem users did not differ on self-presentation behaviours. This study mainly focuses on the effect of selfie taking behaviour on self-esteem.

(Biolcati & Passini, 2018) investigate how various hypothetical expectations of narcissism and self-esteem on selfie-posting behaviours are mediated by various selfie incentives. The results indicated that No difference for sex was found on general selfie-posting behaviors. our results show that females are more active in taking group selfies, while no gender differences on own and partner selfies emerge. Men and women both commonly upload selfies, According to the most recent research (Katz & Crocker, 2015) and gender differences may only be visible in how these selfies are used to portray oneself (Dhir et al., 2016). selfies provide individuals with the potential of enhancing self-disclosure, they also demonstrate some risky and unhealthy behaviours. Therefore, predicting personality traits could be considered an effective variable to sensitize them before the deterioration of their mental health. The overall findings imply that while selfies may give people the opportunity to improve self-disclosure, they also exhibit some dangerous and unhealthy behaviours. (Sharma & Gupta, 2021) Predicting personality features may therefore be a useful variable for sensitising people before their mental health deteriorates.

(Bodroža et al., 2022) have identified three aspects of selfie related behaviour which was measured were the self-presentation through selfies, selfie preoccupation, and upward physical appearance comparison with others' selfies and their relationships with body image concerns and self-esteem. body image and subjective well-being suffer when we compare our selfies to those of others. Self-presentation and the obsession with taking selfies were, however, associated with greater anxiety about receiving a negative appraisal of one's appearance and higher levels of social self-esteem, but they had little association with indications of mental health. (Zhiying & Michael, 2021) suggest that the the early attachment style influences the individual differences and the social media use. Also found out that those who struggle with attachment anxiety are more prone to alter and perfect their selfie faces. Results have shown how the early attachment style influences the individual differences and the social media use. people who struggle with attachment anxiety are more prone to alter and perfect their selfie faces.

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ Objectives of the study

- To assess the relationship between Selfie taking behaviour and Self-esteem among adolescents.
- To assess the gender differences on Selfie taking behaviour among adolescents.
- To assess the gender difference on Self-esteem among adolescents.

➤ Hypothesis

H01: There will be no significant relationship between Selfie taking behaviour on self-esteem among adolescents.

H02: There will be no significant gender differences on Selfie taking behaviour among adolescents.

H03: There will be no significant gender differences on Self-esteem among adolescents.

➤ Research design

Quantitative Research design is used in this study.

➤ Sample

The study was conducted on adolescents from age group 15-24. The sample for the study consists of 80 adolescents (40 males and 40 females) residing different parts of Kerala.

The data was collected using convenient sampling technique.

➤ Tools used

- **Selfitis Behaviour Scale (SBS):** The Selfitis behaviour scale created by Janarthanan & Mark D. Griffiths (2017). The SBS is a 20-item scale designed to measure the selfie taking behavior was used for the current study. The responses were rated on a 5-Point Likert scale (5=strongly agree; 4= Agree; 3= Neither agree or disagree; 2= Disagree; 1= Strongly Disagree).
- **Rosenberg's Self Esteem Scale (RSES):** The Rosenberg's Self Esteem scale created by Rosenberg. M. (1965) was used for the current study. The RSES is a 10-item scale that measures global worthy by measuring both positive and negative feelings about the self. All items are answered by using a 4-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree (4=Strongly agree; 3=Agree, 2=Disagree; 1= Strongly Disagree) and Items 2,5,6,9 are reverse scored.

➤ Statistical Analysis

The results were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. IBM SPSS-2.0 was used for data analysis. Among descriptive statistics, mean and standard deviation were used, among inferential statistics, Pearson's correlation, independent sample t-test and Regression analysis were used to test the hypothesis.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are discussed hypothesis wise as follows.

H01: There will be no significant relationship between Selfie taking behaviour on self- esteem among adolescents.

Table 1 Descriptive statistics and the correlational relationship between Selfie taking behaviour and Self-esteem among adolescents.

Selfie taking behaviour	N	M	SD	1	2
Males	40	60.15	2.62	-	0.07
Females	40	23.81	0.58	0.07	-

*P value>0.05

An analysis of Table 1, shows the mean score for Selfie taking behaviour is 60.15 and Self- esteem is 23.81. In terms of standard deviation for Selfie taking behaviour is 2.62 and for self-esteem is 0.58. To see whether there is a relationship between the two variables, the scores were subject to Pearson’s correlation coefficient. The results presented a correlation (r) value of 0.48 with a corresponding p value of 0.07 which is not significant(p>0.05). Since, the significance value between Selfie taking behaviour and Self-esteem is more than 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant relationship between Selfie taking behaviour and Self-esteem.

On contrary to the above results, a study by Alblooshi, A. (2015) found a significant relationship between low self-esteem levels and posting selfies to boost self-confidence. Another study conducted by Biolcati & Passini (2018) results shows that taking and sharing selfies could result in greater social sensitivity and lower self-esteem of selfie takers.

H02: There will be no significant gender differences on selfie taking behaviour among adolescents.

Table 2 Results of gender difference in Selfie taking behaviour using independent sample t-test

Self-esteem	N	M	SD	t	p
Males	40	62.5	17.78		0.37
				1.26	
Females	40	57.8	15.35		

p>0.05

An analysis of Table 3 shows the mean score of 62.5 and 57.8 for males and females and corresponding standard deviation of 17.78 and 15.35 for selfie taking. The calculated t value for selfie taking behaviour between two groups is 1.26 with corresponding p value of 0.370 which is statistically not found to be significant Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant gender difference on selfie taking behaviour among adolescents.

In line with the above results, the study conducted by Roberta &Stefano (2018) The results indicated that there was no difference for sex was found on general selfie-posting behaviours and females were more active in taking group selfies, while no gender differences on own and partner selfies emerge.

H03: There will be no significant gender differences among adolescents on Self-esteem among adolescents.

Table 3 Results of gender difference in Self-esteem using independent sample t-test

Variables	N	Gender	M	SD	t	p
Self-esteem	40	Males	23.48	3.31		0.18
					-0.81	
	40	Females	24.15			

p>0.05

An Analysis of the Table 3 shows the mean score of 23.48 and 24.15 and corresponding standard deviation of 3.31 and 4.06 for males and females for Self-esteem and a t value of -0.81 and corresponding p value of 0.18 for Self-esteem. which is statistically not found to be significant Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant gender difference in self- esteem among adolescents.

On the contrary to above results, the study conducted by Bolognini et al., (1996) Results of the survey showed that according to gender, girls tend to have a poorer self-esteem than boys, whatever the domains taken into consideration.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are drawn based on the research question raised.

- There is no significant relationship between selfie taking behaviour on self-esteem among adolescents.
- There is no significant gender differences on selfie taking behaviour among adolescents.
- There is no significant gender differences on Self-esteem among adolescents.

SUGGESTIONS

The present findings of the study don’t show any significant relationship between the Selfie taking behaviour and Self-esteem among adolescents. A larger sample size is required for future research in order determine a significant difference and relationship. It requires further research to assess fully the psychosocial impacts that the Selfie taking behaviour might have on the individual. The research should have focused on the stronger variables. Awareness should be created among students especially adolescents regarding selfitis, its harmful effects and to combat the dependencies

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